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Refugees Create Opportunities for Community Good

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Abstract: The current mood of governments of several rich nations is hardly respectful of the principle of non-refoulment. Their policies to restrict refugee applications appears to be influenced by demagogues with nationalist and immigration-hostile policies. A significant proportion of the community in these constituencies do not acknowledge that large parts of their lifestyles carry the flavours of refugee migrants' contributions to the salad bowl in which they live. *The opportunities that arise for adding different dressings to the salad are often taken for granted and go uncelebrated.* In a capitalist world, regularly reminded of the need to acquire more in order to measure up, there is incessant fear of not

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possessing enough to get ahead. It is therefore not surprising that many in the developed world are not keen to absorb displaced people in their communities. Groups and organizations appreciative of the Christian ethos and motivated by the goodwill for displaced people, when pleading the refugee cause, can consider employing a sound bite in public discourse that resonates the defining theme of the miracle of the loaves and fish - *gratitude for engaging with goodness*.

Keywords: Refugees, Miracle, Loaves, Fish, Gratitude, Sound Bite

Introduction: Refugees Fleeing Ancestral Lands is a Social Movement

The saga of besieged people seeking to run away from their ancestral lands is not new. History and myths of countless nations are replete with catastrophes and crises that have compelled people to flee, simply to preserve life and limb. In the last century alone, millions sought new homes as they escaped the ravages of the two world wars that devastated most of Europe and parts of Asia (China, Japan, East India, Burma and Malaya). This is in addition to the ravages of famines in the Africa and parts of Asia and the Americas, and localised wars, genocides and religious, economic, ethnic and social persecutions. In the more recent past refugees have been forced to flee from military crackdowns in several parts of the world, particularly in the context of conflicts over decolonisation, state formation, and incorporation into the bipolar world order of the Cold War (Zolberg et al. 1989).

Millions of people are also displaced every year by development/infrastructure projects such as dams, airports, roads, luxury housing, conservation areas and game parks. The World Bank puts their number at 10 million a year. Some may be able to rebuild their livelihoods, but many experience permanent impoverishment and marginalization (Cernea & McDowell 2000; World Commission on Dams 2000).

Typically, it is rural dwellers, ethnic minorities and indigenous people who suffer, while elites and transnational companies benefit from the disruptive chaos (Roy 1999). In addition, many people have to migrate or flee because of environmental degradation, natural disasters and industrial accidents or pollution.

It is important to note that forced migration is not the result of a string of unconnected emergencies. Contemporary sociology considers refugee migration to be both a result and a cause of social transformation in beleaguered countries. Asylum-seeking refugees are a form of expression of global inequalities and societal crises, which have gained in volume and importance since the superseding of the East-West bipolar world order.

Castles (2003) believes that refugee displacement in the epoch of globalisation is a social movement rather than just a geographical relocation. The sociology of refugee seeking migration has to be seen in the broader understanding of the social transformation processes inherent in the emerging global social order (or disorder). These mass movements of distraught people seeking to make a fresh start in safer environments have often proved to be a challenge for host countries to absorb them without fear of dislocating their geopolitical balance. Refugee policies repeatedly fail because policymakers refuse to see migration as a dynamic social process linked to broader patterns of social transformation. A moot question is whether self-obsessed politicians, keen on pushing their own agendas, are able to view with compassion impoverished refugees and acknowledge that they will bring innovative approaches and new opportunities for communities that adopt them in host countries.

1. United Nations Mandates Absorption of Displaced People

Political leaders and bureaucrats frequently regard migration as something that can be turned on and off like a tap through laws and policies. In order to ensure that countries of the world behave with a sense of propriety with regard to refugee protection, the United Nations in 1951 established the principle that the refugee problem is a matter of concern to the entire international community and must be addressed in the context of international cooperation and burden-sharing. At the universal level, the most comprehensive legally binding international instrument defining standards for the treatment of refugees is the United Nations Convention relating to the Status of Refugees of 28th July 1951. This Convention was adopted in the immediate post-World War II period, when the refugee problems confronting the international community, were mainly those of refugees of European origin. After the adoption of the 1951 Convention, refugee situations began to arise in different regions of the world, which were not in any way related to pre-1951 events. This led to efforts to make the Convention fully applicable in all-new refugee situations, based on the recognition that the 1951 Convention should become the universal international instrument for the protection of refugees. It resulted in the United Nations Refugee Protocol which was opened for accession on 31st January 1967. To date, 149 States in all regions of the world have become parties to the 1951 UN Refugee Convention and/or to the 1967 Refugee Protocol. These key legal documents highlighted the principle of *non-refoulement* and decreed that every asylum seeker and refugee needs to be guaranteed a safe place to live and mandated that signatories of the convention were obliged to absorb displaced people in their communities.

The principle of non-refoulement is the established cornerstone of refugee protection. Under international refugee law, it prohibits States from expelling or returning (“refouler”) a refugee in any manner whatsoever to the frontiers of territories where their life

or freedom would be threatened on account of their race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion.

2. Christian Spirit of Embracing Refugees

Very early in the Bible, in Exodus 23:9 God exhorts the Israelites who fled from Egypt to seek refuge in another land “Do not oppress a foreigner; you yourselves know how it feels to be foreigners because you were foreigners”. In Leviticus 19:33-34, God once again urges Israel that “When a foreigner resides among you in your land, do not mistreat them. The foreigner residing among you must be treated as your native-born. Love them as yourself, for you were foreigners in Egypt”. In recounting the references made in the gospels with regard to the obligation to refugees, Costello & Kal (2018) identify Jesus himself as a refugee, when his parents were forced to flee with the young Jesus to Egypt to escape the murderous intent of Herod (Matt 2:13-23). Costello et al. (2018) point out that in Jesus’ own ministry, the duty to care for the refugee is seen in the overarching question in Jesus’ teaching: “Who is my neighbour?” (Luke 10:29). The famous Parable of the Good Samaritan directs the Christian to care for the stranger regardless of their background. Similarly, in the parable of the sheep and the goats in Matthew 25:31-46, Jesus spoke of how the righteous should welcome the stranger. “I was hungry and you gave me food, I was thirsty and you gave me drink, I was a stranger and you welcomed me.”

In Christian thinking, all human beings are made in the image of God and everyone, native citizen or refugee deserves respect and protection. We have been created by God to love our neighbour; it is part of the greatest commandment that Jesus gave (Matt 22:39). In reference to refugees, this means not turning away from the needs of the world’s refugees. The early Christian movement continued the example of Jesus in

this care for their neighbours. The sociologist, Rodney Stark (1997), points out that the early church grew very rapidly during the first centuries after the Resurrection of Jesus because the love shown by Christians to all was genuinely persuasive. During famine and plague, Christians, at immense cost and risk, cared for the weak and sick who had been abandoned, not just their fellow Christians. A hallmark of true Christian faith, according to Costello and Kal (2018), is that it welcomes refugees with open hearts and arms, and advocates on their behalf. Refugees too are our brothers and sisters in the family of humanity. Since the late 1970s, Van Haran (2021) reports that Christian denominational offices and organizations in Canada, in what is known as Canada's Private Sponsorship Model, have mobilised support of private citizens and civil-society groups to resettle more than 770000 refugees. In recent years, countries including Argentina, Australia, France, Germany, New Zealand, and Spain have undertaken or committed to similar programs.

3. Refugees Boost Social Capital and Economies of Adopting Countries

In the past few decades, a significant number of residence visas have been granted to asylum seekers and refugees by western democracies. Communities in these countries that have helped to rehabilitate the new arrivals from crisis-torn countries have benefited immensely from the integration of immigrants in mainstream society. Turks in Germany, North Africans in France, New Commonwealth immigrants in the United Kingdom, and Mexicans in the United States all brought in new and varied religious, cultural and social practices. From cuisine to performing arts to sports, education and management of the body politic it is not unusual to see the perceptible foreign influence in the tapestry of the social fabric.

Importantly the economies of the adopting western countries have improved significantly by the interplay of labour supply and demand for goods and services provided by the refugee immigrant community. Governments in the United States, Italy

and elsewhere tacitly use asylum and undocumented migration as a way of meeting labour needs without publicly admitting the need for unskilled migration. Most of these countries continue to post higher levels of GNP (Gross National Product) and GDP (Gross Domestic Product) than those countries that have secured themselves against the arrival of asylum seekers and refugees (Castles, 2003).

4. Western Intervention – Agent Provocateur of Terrorism

Often it is not realized that the western countries which historically accommodated asylum seekers and refugees have in some measure directly or indirectly contributed to the case of political upheavals and turmoil that set off their displacement.

Western economic interests (such as the trade in oil, diamonds, coltan or arms) have played an important part in starting or prolonging local wars. At a broader level, trade, investment and intellectual property regimes that favour the industrialised nations maintain underdevelopment in the countries whose economies are already poorly managed. During the last 25 years of unrest in the Middle East, western mercantilism has been in its flourish and has contributed significantly to economic growth in western economies. Unfortunately, this aggrandisement of some of the western nations has resulted in leaving large swathes of territory, in which these western nations have been militarily involved, in very impecunious condition. Castles (2003) believes that the West does more to cause refugee migration crises than to stop it, through enforcing an international economic and political order that causes underdevelopment and conflict.

According to Castles (2003), impoverished economies generally also mean these weak states foster predatory ruling cliques who tout that western intrusion in the domestic affairs

of their countries was essentially a grab of their country's wealth. Intent on avenging revenge for the loot of their country as well as "administering justice" to those sympathetic to westerners, local homegrown militants typically engage in a reign of terror. The inevitable human rights abuse this terror brings in its wake is the reason for the surge of locals fleeing their ancestral homes to seek a safer abode in foreign countries.

Most often the terror groups do not stay localised but seek vindication of the West's military atrocities within western countries against, what they consider, criminal Christian forces. The past 20 years have witnessed some horrific crimes committed by terrorist groups in various parts of the world claiming ownership of the terror attacks as retaliation for western atrocities in their countries of origin. These acts of violence have aroused hatred of the countries from which most asylum seekers and refugees originate.

5. Internal Security Threat is Code for Fear of Losing Out

The hatred that has understandably taken over the mindset of western societies when they see the carnage perpetrated by terrorists has been a fertile ground for the far-right conservative views that peddle xenophobia and jingoism. These groups, canvassing themselves as looking after the national interests, have positioned immigrants coming from countries, in which the allies had gone to help, as potential homegrown terrorists and a threat to the internal safety of their country. However it is not the refugees and asylum seekers who create problems in their counties of adoption, but they are unfortunately demonised and get the social opprobrium of the public. Fear-mongering is a tactic used by far-right political parties and groups to distance the population's sympathies from refugees. According to Castles (2003), following the events of September 11, 2001, refugees have been branded as a sinister transnational threat to national security – even though none of the September 11 terrorists were refugees or asylum seekers. The "internal threat to security" is

used as a code for the fear that immigrant asylum seekers and refugees will take the jobs of the locals and outshine locals in competitive situations due to their grit and diligence. Every time there is an attack on civilian sites in the western world there is a suspicion that the immigrant erstwhile refugee or asylum seeker community has been the perpetrator, and vindicates the far right's views of the internal threat to security. In almost all instances these suspicions have proved to be baseless because asylum seekers and refugees are most thankful for the new lease of life that their country of adoption has given them and are generally keen on making a fist of life by actively contributing to society. Also, treating refugees with hostility or discriminating against them based on fear of their possible radicalization allow militant organizations to recruit them from within the ranks of disaffected refugee populations, thus setting off a self-fulfilling prophecy.

6. Giving Thanks - the Defining Theme of Miracle of Loaves and Fish

The innate fear that refugees will deplete the resources of their host country and deprive the country's citizens of their privileges might be allayed by the scripture narrative (John 6:1-15) of the multitude of 5000 men, women and children being fed by a limited resource of five loaves and two fish. Christ was filled with compassion for the hungry disposition of the hapless thousands who had followed him. He dismissed the conservative views of his apostle Philip and other apostles to turn them away and was not deterred to feed them himself with the meagre stock available. What is often lost in representing the storyline is the focus on the *defining moment* of Jesus "*giving Thanks*". Mark (6:41) in his narrative of the loaves and fish, recounts "Taking the five loaves and the two fish and looking up to heaven, he (Jesus) gave thanks and broke the loaves". Here is Jesus extolling

his Father in an abbreviated manner of the opening of the Lord's prayer (which he taught his disciples how to pray, Matthew 6, 9-13) "*Our Father, who art in Heaven, Hallowed be Thy Name, Thy Kingdom come, Thy will be done on earth-----*". By looking up to heaven, Jesus affirms the embrace of the Father's plan, and expresses gratitude, which is the corollary of extolling, for engaging with his Father's Kingdom. St. Thomas Aquinas, an eminent Doctor of the church in the 13th century, asserts in *Contra Gentiles*, IV, xix that unequivocal acceptance of the Divine plan is to trust that all things given by God (compassion for the crowds that followed Jesus and stayed behind till late, the availability of paltry provisions of five loaves and two fish) are latently good, *even when the goodness is not evident*. Jesus naturally upholds engagement with goodness ("looking up to heaven, he gave thanks").

"Giving Thanks" is translated in Greek as "*Eucharisto*" which is also the root of the term "Gratitude" and "Grace". The Greek word for gratitude is built on the word for grace, "*charis*". In this narrative the *grace* which was manifest in Jesus' action to distribute a paltry meal was the catalyst that sparked the alchemy of multiplication of five loaves and two fish, feeding everybody gathered, with spare food remaining to fill 12 baskets. Miserable refugees once resettled could well spur opportunities for their hosts to advance all things good for themselves and their community.

7. Developed Countries Hesitant to Accommodate Refugees

Countries in the recent past that accepted most of the world refugees as a percentage of their population do not feature among those which offer some of the best qualities of life. The countries that have received the most refugees in relation to their population during the period 2011-2020 include Lebanon 19.5%, Jordan 10.5%, Nauru 5.9 %, Liberia 4.1%, Uganda 3.7 %, Sudan 2.6 % and South Sudan 2.5 %. These emigrant countries, despite having to deal with vast sections of their own impoverished people, have

opened their doors to the world's distraught though sometimes unwittingly. All of these countries border the states from which the threatened people are escaping. Invariably the refugees are housed in conditions that often lack basic amenities, but at least provide them with a safe haven from the life-threatening dangers they face back home. However, not surprisingly, people escaping their homes because of threat and fear would like to be accommodated in politically stable countries that offer permanent settlement without disruption rather than seek refuge in the neighbours of their homeland who often struggle with political instability and economic mismanagement. It is unfortunate that countries that enjoy some of the best quality of life, as reported by Ireland, (2021), namely, US, UK, France and Australia, are often resistant to letting in displaced people. Schwöbel-Patel & Deger (2017) believe that in such countries refugees are regularly framed in a narrow way through legal images, metaphors and discursive structures that obscure the frequent complicity of receiving states in the plight of refugees. Such myopic framing is exemplified by the attitude towards people fleeing countries where Western military intervention in the name of humanitarianism has destabilised the political and economic situation further, and has consequently increased the flow of people who have no choice but to leave.

Understandably, refugees consider their moral right for permanent settlement in countries that were involved in ostensibly bringing stability to their homelands. It is estimated by United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) in its report of 2010 that the annual applications of asylum seekers in Western Europe, Australia, Canada and the US combined are close to one million. Also, all of these countries were signatories of the Geneva Convention of 1951 mandating the obligation of signatories to rehabilitate refugees. However, the fairly narrow

definition of the 1951 UN Refugee Convention applying only to people forced to leave their countries due to individual persecution on specific grounds has allowed the setup by developed countries of a ‘non-arrival regime’ to prevent refugees entering and making asylum claims. These regimes have raised common questions around who qualifies as a refugee and construction of distinctions between undeserving migrants (illegals) and deserving refugees (legals). Indeed, a public debate on who is deserving has led to accusations of ‘bogus’ asylum seekers and ‘fake’ refugees.

8. Sound Bite Extolling the Goodness of Resettling Impoverished Refugees

The current mood of governments of several rich nations is hardly respectful of the principle of non-refoulement. Their policies to restrict refugee applications appears to be influenced by demagogues with nationalist and immigration-hostile policies. *A significant proportion of the community in these constituencies do not acknowledge that large parts of their lifestyles carry the flavours of refugee migrants’ contributions to the salad bowl in which they live.* The opportunities that arise for adding different dressings to the salad are often taken for granted and go uncelebrated.

In a capitalist world, regularly reminded of the need to acquire more in order to measure up, there is incessant fear of not possessing enough to get ahead. The quality of life that most citizens of these countries enjoy is usually disregarded in their inevitable rat race. Within large sections of these communities the refugee is likely to be considered as ‘Schrödinger’s immigrant’, who is ‘simultaneously stealing your job and too lazy to work’ (Rowthorn & Růžička, 2017). According to Schwöbel-Patel et al. (2017), the public influenced by demagogues, fearing that refugees exercise agency through labour and through making demands on state resources, allow their concern of being deprived of opportunities and privileges dominate their moral psyche. It is

therefore not surprising that many in the developed world are not keen to absorb displaced people in their communities.

Groups and organizations appreciative of the Christian ethos and motivated by the goodwill for displaced people, when pleading the refugee cause, can consider employing a sound bite in public discourse that resonates the defining theme of the miracle of the loaves and fish - *gratitude for engaging with goodness*. The sound bite typically appreciates the virtue inherent in resettling impoverished refugees. According to Danielle Allen (2008), UPS Foundation Professor in the School of Social Science, sound bites have the capacity to be the basis of building common understandings of who and what we are, as well as the capacity of the principle to motivate action. Allen (2008) further proffers that sound bites more often than not become authoritative and part of commonly spoken language. One of the more famous sound bites is from the inaugural address of President J F Kennedy in 1961 “Ask not what your country can do for you—ask what you can do for your country.” The phrase, which has a crisp, seemingly effortless ring to it has, inspired countless Americans and others around the globe. The sound bite is the climax of the overall theme of sacrifice for the cause of liberty. It suggests that individual Americans and individual citizens of all nations should consider what actions they can take to advance freedom for humanity and be willing to perform them.

Conclusion

Ben Patterson (2011), in his book *Muscular Faith: How to Strengthen One’s Heart, Mind, and Soul for the Only Test that Matters*, suggests that grace predicates gratitude. He quotes Karl Barth, the noted Swiss theologian and well-known Christian thinker, as asking “How else can one be but profoundly grateful when such a thing as grace happens? It

is grace that evokes gratitude like the voice of an echo". It is fair to say that politicians as a class are self-obsessed in pursuing their vested interests and most are unlikely to canvass the cause of hapless refugees if the agenda goes against their political fortunes. However, when the sound bite becomes part of vernacular, *the voice* from the sound bite will find an *echo* among the body politic, which could compel them to consider that resettling pitiable refugees, in the emergent social order, creates opportunities for the good of the community. The resonance in the echo also has the capacity to influence neoliberal political leaders that participation of refugees in the community will not deplete state resources but contribute to creating a distributive surplus.

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